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Abstract:

This document describes the evolutions of Aioli and the new features implemented within the framework of the SSHOC project since its previous version. The development version of Aioli is currently hosted on one of the CNRS MAP servers and can be accessed through the following link: <https://absinthe.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index>. The beta testing version of the platform will be available at <https://beta.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index> (send mail to contact@aioli.cloud for an account creation).

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CNRS-MAP	Adeline Manuel	adeline.manuel@map.cnrs.fr
CNRS-MAP	Livio De Luca	livio.deluca@map.cnrs.fr
CNRS-MAP	Isabelle Cao	isabelle.cao@map.cnrs.fr
CNRS-MAP	Theo Zanetti	theo.zanetti@map.cnrs.fr

Executive Summary

Archaeologists, architects, engineers, materials specialists, teachers, curators, and restorers of cultural property, contribute to the daily knowledge and conservation of heritage artefacts. For many years, the development of digital technologies has produced important results in the collection, visualisation and indexing of digital resources. Whilst these advances have made it possible to introduce new tools that are making documentation practises evolve within the cultural heritage community, the management of multi-dimensional and multi-format data introduces new problems and challenges, in particular the development of relevant analysis and interpretation methods, the sharing and correlation of heterogeneous data among several actors and contexts, and the centralised archiving of documentation results for long-term preservation purposes. Despite their different approaches and tools for observation, description and analysis, the actors of cultural heritage documentation all have a common interest and central focus: the heritage object, the physical one, whether it is a site, a building, a sculpture, a painting, a work of art, or an archaeological fragment.

This is the starting point for the development of "aioli", a reality-based 3D annotation platform, which allows a multidisciplinary community to build semantically enriched 3D descriptions of heritage artefacts from simple images and spatialized annotations coupled with additional resources. This platform introduces an innovative framework for the comprehensive, large-scale collaborative documentation of cultural heritage by integrating state-of-the-art technological components (image-based 3D reconstruction, 2D-3D spreading and correlation of semantic annotations, multi-layered analysis of qualitative and quantitative attributes, etc.) within a cloud infrastructure accessible via web interfaces from PCs, tablets, and smartphones online and onsite.

This document describes the evolutions of Aioli and the new features implemented within the framework of the SSHOC project since its previous version. The development version of Aioli is currently hosted on one of the CNRS MAP servers and can be accessed through the following link: <https://absinthe.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index>. A beta testing version of the platform will be available at <https://beta.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index> (send mail to contact@aioli.cloud for an account creation).

Abbreviations and Acronyms

SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (National Center for Scientific Research)
MAP	Modèles et simulation pour l'Architecture et le Patrimoine (Models and simulations for Architecture and Heritage)
CH	Cultural Heritage
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

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1. Introduction

This document describes the second deliverable of the SSHOC Task 4.6 “Semantic annotation of Heritage Science Data” within the WP4 “Innovations in Data Production”. This task is focused on the integration of an innovative web service for the reality-based 3D annotation of heritage artefacts within the SSHOC infrastructure.

For the last few years the cross-disciplinary community working on digital technologies applied to cultural heritage has been involved in national and international projects for building next generation tools and information systems for analysing the state of conservation of heritage artefacts, studying their temporal transformations, extracting their morphological features, correlating heterogeneous data coming from several disciplines.

Moving from data-driven to a semantic-driven digital documentation approach is an essential challenge today, especially in Cultural Heritage (CH), where knowledge is always the result of a combination of complementary skills and disciplinary profiles.

The main purpose is to merge all these aspects (geometry, visual appearance, semantics) within an integrated documentation approach built on an informative continuity merging the acquisition, analysis, and interpretation phases within a collaborative framework.

This report details the evolutions of Aioli and the new features implemented within the framework of the SSHOC project since its previous version. The development version of Aioli is currently hosted on one of the CNRS MAP servers and can be accessed through the following link: <https://absinthe.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index>.

A beta testing version of the platform will be available at <https://beta.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index> (send mail to contact@aioli.cloud for an account creation). The code is stored on an internal Gitlab depository at the CNRS MAP, which is currently only accessible via VPN connection.

2. Core principles

Managing heterogeneous data for documenting cultural heritage artefacts needs for a stable denominator (from a conceptual and technical point of view) for structuring data & annotations coming from a continuous process of observation & analysis carried out by multiple actors (with different profile and description approaches). The starting point of the aioli project¹ is to consider the heritage object (the physical one) at the heart of the documentation process by crossing “reality-based 3D” and “semantic description” in a strongly integrated way. By correlating simple images (probably the stablest support for registering field observations since the invention of photography), the aioli platform generates a dynamic 3D morphologic scaffolding for structuring data & annotations. At the same time, this data structure becomes a way of enabling the communication between several actors involved in the documentation and the study of the same object. This is made by interlinking all phases that characterise the overall documentation process within an ‘informative continuum’ by combining three essential features :

- A continuous 3D mapping and annotation process. The approach creates a sort of bridge between the real object and its digital representation by introducing a solution for memorising spatialised annotations made by different actors.
- A morphology-based documentation framework. Based on a spatial overlapping factor, a multi-layers description model allows the simultaneous structuring of data and geometry as well as the continuous correlation of semantic annotations (with relative attributes).
- A flexible & scalable technology. This platform is built on a cloud computing service allowing the gathering, processing and sharing of semantically-enriched 3D data within online and onsite documentation scenarios.

This platform introduces an original informative linkage between the physical object space and its digital representation by facing to two interconnected technical issues: the onsite retrieval of structured information according to the physical object's annotation; the onsite collection and processing of new data to be spatially referenced and semantically correlated with previous data. This is done by integrating the following features:

- An incremental image-based 3D spatialisation process to manage the geometric merging of several images coming from different actors at different temporal states²;

¹ Aioli: a reality-based 3D annotation platform for the collaborative documentation of heritage artefacts: www.aioli.cloud

² Pamart A., Morlet F., De Luca L. A fully automated incremental photogrammetric processing dedicated for collaborative remote-computing workflow. Proceedings of 8th Intl. Workshop 3D-ARCH “3D Virtual Reconstruction and Visualization of Complex Architectures”, 6–8 February 2019, Bergamo, Italy. Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLII-2/W9, 573-580, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W9-573-2019>.

- A 2D/3D annotation framework enabling users to draw, visualise and register relevant surface regions by handling simple 2D images spatially oriented around a dynamic 3D representation³ ;
- A multi-layered morphology-based data structuring model to accurately describe real objects in all their geometric complexity and according to multidisciplinary observations.

By relying on the automation of photogrammetric image spatialization processes and the possibility of gathering, processing, and distributing large amounts of data via cloud computing, the heart of the platform resides on a multidimensional correlation engine, based on a cloud computing infrastructure. Thanks to this process (Fig.1), the annotations carried out on any image of the object are automatically projected on all the other images (past, present, and future) and continually correlated geometrically, visually and semantically, with other annotations with a near spatial location. By spontaneously gathering data and annotations from several users on the same object, this platform then makes it possible to gradually build a framework for the archiving of resources, as well as for the comparison of observations and analyses carried out within multidisciplinary studies.

Figure 1. 2D/3D spreading of annotation within a set of spatially-oriented photographs

³ Manuel A., Stefani C., De Luca L., Véron P. A hybrid approach for the semantic annotation of spatially oriented images, IJHDE (International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era), Volume 3 Number 2, pp 305-320. Multi Science Publishing, 2014.

A first version of the platform implementing these principles has been developed allowing to organize a first beta testing campaign.

3. First beta testing program

In order to try out the experimental features of Aioli, a beta-testing programme started on October 2018. This programme has involved selected actors of cultural heritage, scientific and professional community. Within this framework, a wide range of heritage artefacts, belonging to different scales and photographed by different sensors, have been used for experimenting the implemented features (archaeological sites, buildings, archaeological artefacts, archaeological fragments, and parietal art, ...). Different devices were successfully tested for the photogrammetric acquisition (digital reflex, tablets, and smartphones), also including UAV-based acquisitions. The aim of this program was not only to pinpoint technical difficulties, but also to collect feedback on the features and discuss the issues and the challenges of the data sharing (images, 3D models, annotations, descriptions, ...). This beta-testing programme also has represented the opportunity to explore and design the potential uses of the platform within the CH community.

Within the specific context of SSHOC, the main activities related to the task 4.6 and to the development of the Aioli project have been presented and discussed during the WP4 meeting at the SSHOC Kickoff event (March 11-12, 2019, Utrecht), during the WP4 Workshop “Developing the SSHOC Reference Ontology” organised by FORTH (May 21-22, Heraklion, Crete), as well as during several video meetings with WP4 task leaders and members. These meetings have been used as framework for defining the specifications of the new features to be developed in the platform in the deliverable 4.16 ‘Specification of the new features of the Aioli platform’.

The general feedback from users and colleagues involved in the above mentioned actions is very positive: Aioli represents an effective framework for gathering, documenting and analysing CH artefacts within multidisciplinary contexts. But the informatics implementation presents some limitations today and new features should be introduced in order to foster the use of aioli into a wider community.

4. New version of Aioli

The new version of Aioli has been developed while maintaining the core functionalities of the first version (as described in deliverable 4.16). A redesign of the architecture has improved the robustness of the platform as well as the possibility to deploy it on a larger scale. Numerous features have also been introduced in order to facilitate the use of the platform and to offer new tools for more varied descriptions scenarios of CH objects.

4.1 The technical robustness of the platform

The beta testing of Aioli platform has demonstrated a great interest from the users of the Cultural Heritage community. In order to increase the use scenarios, it is necessary to face technical issues related to the management of large volumes of data.

Within the Aioli new version, a database which would be able to support the massive and collaborative use of Aioli platform in the near future is used. The solution is to adopt a no-sql document-oriented database, a type of database that meets all these constraints. The choice has been set up on CouchDB (developed by the Apache Foundation) that allows us many benefits. Among them, the request via HTTP which allows the creation of heterogeneous documents, the retrieval of data directly from the application in JSON format, and its event-oriented design, particularly appropriate for the multi-user collaborative uses.

The robustness of the Aioli platform for large-scale use is also demonstrated by its operation in a server appliance - soler3 - which supports multiple simultaneous connections on large projects. Aioli is today running on a server appliance composed of 90 cores (developing 180 high frequency threads equivalent to 250 gigaflops) of computing power, completed by 256GB of RAM and supported by 8TB of storage. The new version of Aioli has been designed to provide a technical solution for easily installing the platform in larger server appliances.

A beta version of the Aioli platform is developed to allow access to all users even if they are not on the CNRS-MAP network. The beta version is available online and is already in use for a few selected users. For now the creation of an account is not open to everyone and requires human intervention to create accounts. The possibility of a user creating his own account directly on the beta version exists and is just not enabled yet. It would be active when the new version would be officially released on a dedicated server. Thanks to those many progress in the development and implementations, the objective is the diffusion within the Cultural Heritage community at the international scale.

4.2 Collaborative framework

The multi-user's aspects in Aioli platform are central so the interface for the user-end uses was adapted to a social network-like approach.

In the settings, users could set their discoverability (called visibility, which could either be public or private), to enable the other users to see them within the community. This setting will allow the users

who would like to remain invisible to do so, while giving the opportunity to the others to share their work to some/all of the other users. When a user's visibility is set to public, all other users can invite him as a collaborator, which then allows them to interact and to work on shared projects.

Collaborative projects can be defined by two categories of settings: the sharing and the visibility options (Figure 2). The sharing option allows specified collaborators to open the workspace and use the application to annotate regions, describe layers and regions and consult the project. The visibility option allows anyone - with an Aioli account - to access any project set to visible.

Figure 2. Projects settings interface

These two settings satisfy the Aioli's requirement to offer a collaborative framework that both respects the respective confidentiality constraints and gives the chance to disseminate one's work for new cooperation opportunities.

4.3 Interoperability

TACO, the MicMac-based image processing process for point cloud reconstruction integrated into Aioli, can handle most image datasets taken according to a specific acquisition protocol. However, in the case of complex objects or complex multimodal acquisitions, this process can fail because it follows a series of steps that do not allow the selection of processing options that would be necessary for these particular sites.

Thus the possibility of importing a project processed outside the platform is possible. This modality implies the creation of an archive following a precise structure based on the MicMac file structure. Projects processed outside the platform by MicMac can therefore be easily integrated into the platform.

As MicMac is not necessarily the most accessible and therefore the most used photogrammetry software, the possibility of importing projects processed by other software has been studied. A lot of feedback shows that Metashape is widely used in the Cultural Heritage community. A script for converting Metashape data to an archive respecting the MicMac data structure that can be imported into Aioli was therefore implemented. This script simply runs within Metashape and directly creates the archive to be imported into the platform.

4.4 Projects' Georeferencing and scaling

Georeferencing allows the location of an object in space by assigning geographic coordinates. This location information is a means of positioning objects according to their geographical position in relation to each other. In the new version of Aioli, each heritage asset can be associated with geographical coordinates and then automatically placed on a map showing its position (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Georeferencing interface

For the scaling, a specific modality of project creation has been set up. In addition to the images, two files (a 2D file and a 3D file) can be loaded when creating the project. The 2D file contains the coordinates (i,j) of points identified in the images and the 3D file contains the coordinates (x,y,z) of these same points. These files are used to constrain the generation of the point cloud and therefore to define the scale and orientation of the project.

4.5 Use of controlled vocabulary

Collaborative projects mean multiple actors that each have their own semantic specificities rather it is related to their domain or natural language. Controlled vocabularies are one solution to this terminology variation that can cause misunderstanding between collaborators and data indexation confusion. Moreover, there are many vocabularies related to Cultural Heritage structured in RDF - the standard for the publication within the Semantic Web - to benefit from for reuse. The integration of controlled vocabularies in Aioli platform also responds to the SSHOC project work on an RDF based architecture using different SKOS thesauri.

Controlled vocabularies are implemented in Aioli through a docker container of an already existed web-based multilingual thesaurus management tool dedicated to the management of vocabularies (conforms to ISO 25964-1 2011 and ISO 25964-2:2012 standards Information and documentation - Thesauri and interoperability with other vocabularies). This tool, named Opentheso and developed at the CNRS (National Centre for Scientific Research, France), offers interface elements to create, insert and manage lists of concepts. It also allows alignments with external controlled vocabularies. This implementation also takes into account a word auto-completion function as well as the integration of URI (Uniform Resource Identifier) elements to navigate through the terms and definitions of internal vocabularies as well as external resources. The new version of Opentheso (Opentheso2) (Figure 4) has been deployed within a Docker container. This new version integrates advanced functionalities and in particular the provision of a complete REST Webservice.

Figure 4. Opentheso interface

- TACO: the image processing for the reconstruction of the point cloud from images (Figure 6)
- Mayonnaise: the point cloud and image indexing process (Figure 7)
- Ketchoupi: the semi-automatic propagation of annotation process (Figure 8)

Figure 6. Mapping of TACO

Figure 7. Mapping of Mayonnaise

Figure 8. Mapping of Ketchoupi

These three processes were modelled on the same basis as the description of the heritage asset and annotation process by using CIDOC-CRM high level classes and specific classes such as CRMdig.

4.7 Online publication

The sharing and dissemination of an annotated project within a community is a crucial issue for the Aioli project. Collaboration modalities already allow several actors to work on the same project through the management of rights on a project. Each project owner can define a set of collaborators who can integrate their own annotations on a project. However, opening up a project to a community means that it is not necessary to create an account on Aioli for each person who simply wants to consult the results.

Spritz, a specific viewer, is therefore being developed to allow the sharing and dissemination of Aioli projects on a wider scale. This viewer aims to embed Aioli scenes within a web page (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Spritz interface

This viewer also allows loading several projects (Figure 6) linked to the same heritage asset within the same scene (if the different projects have been properly referenced to each other). In order to be able to compare the annotations, a manual system of merging groups and layers (Figure 7) is being put in place in order to be able to create a new project resulting from several projects (Figure 8) linked to the same heritage asset. As this viewer does not require a connection to an account, the possibility of importing a file translating the configuration of the new scene can be downloaded in order to save the composition of the generated scene.

Figure 10. Selection of projects to be loaded

Figure 11. Composition of the merge scene

Figure 12. Composed scene

Moreover modalities for exporting the scene data and annotations in CIDOC-CRM format based on the mapping are actually being set up.

5. New beta testing campaign

A new beta testing campaign is planned for early 2022. On that occasion aioli will be onboard on the EOSC Portal.

This campaign will open the use of the platform to the CH community and will allow to collect user feedback on the new features implemented. Due to technical limitations (storage capacity of the server currently used), registration for this campaign will be on demand. Opening an account will not be free but will require sending a message through a contact form. In the future, when a dedicated server will be set up, users will be free to open an account. The beta testing version will be opened on a different web link (<https://beta.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index>) from the development version so as not to interfere with the use of the features.

6. Conclusion

The new functionalities of Aioli within the framework of SSHOC allow us to consider opening the platform to a new beta testing campaign at the beginning of 2022 and to collect feedback from users to address any remaining bugs. All information for this campaign will be available on the website www.aioli.cloud and access to the platform will be via the following link: <https://beta.aioli.map.cnrs.fr/index> (send mail to contact@aioli.cloud for an account creation). By the end of the project, the online publication functionalities will be finalised and will allow the dissemination of annotated projects in Aioli on a larger scale.

Several options are envisaged to assure the long-term use of the platform by the user community. First, opening up to an open community by distributing the code under an open-source licence could provide assistance in defining and developing new functionalities. On the other hand, the transmission on specific uses to private companies ensuring the hosting and maintenance of the platform is also envisaged.

To continue the development of the platform and the integration of new functionalities, several projects (EU and ANR) involving Aioli have been submitted and are awaiting evaluation. A collaboration with a company reusing server waste heat for building heating is underway on questions of data processing and extraction from Aioli.

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